

Deaths, Destructions and Displacements (DDD): The Impact of Boko Harm Insurgency on Education Development in North-East Nigeria

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Abstract

Boko Haram insurgency has affected every sector in the Northern part of Nigeria, especially the Northeast region. It is understood that even before the emergence of the Boko Haram in Northeastern part of Nigeria, the region was characterized with the poorest rate of socio-economic and human development index. The paper examined consequences of Boko Haram insurgency on education sector in Northeast Nigeria. The research being qualitative in nature, obtained data through the primary and secondary sources and analyzed thematically. The study found that there are several associated consequences of Boko Harm insurgency on education in the region including but not limited to death, destruction, and displacement. The consequences have had serious implications of manpower shortage, destruction of infrastructure and facilities, displacement of teachers and students, and the mass abduction of school children among others. It is noted that these consequences have repeatedly posed a serious threat or set back to conducive teaching and learning environment much needed for by teachers 'and students alike and by extension to the education sector at large. To advance a conducive teaching and learning atmosphere, the research recommends that government and stakeholders alike must work hand in hand to provide practical and realistic steps to address the recurring security challenges associated with schools. It is believed that with an enhanced safe learning space for both teachers and students alike their performance in major education outcomes will improve as well enhance the overall educational development not only in the Northeast region but across Nigeria as a whole.

Keywords: *Armed Conflict; Boko Haram; Insurgency; Education; Mass Abduction; Teachers; Students; Northeast Nigeria.*

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Introduction

Boko Haram are terrorist group of people formed by some few Islamic sect to fight against western education and the activities related to its operations in the northern region. According to Walker (2012) Boko Haram sects Jama'atu Ahlus-Sunnah Lidda'Awati Wal Jihad, known world over as Boko Haram, is

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a terrorist Islamic sect in Nigeria that has formed mayhem across the northeastern part of Nigeria and in the federal capital, Abuja. Its fierce bouts on administration offices, the United Nations, mosques, and churches loom to disrupt the nation. Boko Haram appeared in the early 2000s as a small Sunni Islamic sect supporting a firm clarification and execution of Islamic law for Nigerians and Nigeria (Lauren Ploch Blanchard, 2014). Since then, Nigeria is experiencing a high flood of insecurity, particularly in the northeastern region by the insurgent group called: The Jama'atu Ahlus-Sunnah lidda Awati Wal-Jihad generally known as Boko Haram.

Giving this, Musa (2011) opined that Boko Haram stated their activities since 2001 but was not popular until 2009 when they engaged vigorously in the religious ferocity which happened in the Northeastern region. The name Boko Haram was derived from the Hausa language, in English, it means "Western education is sinful". However, this sect of people rejects everything related to western education and origin, precisely the western education, its principles, and schemes. "Boko in English means western education, while Haram means sinful. It is observed that Boko Haram rejects not only western education but western culture and modern science as well. In a view of Yusuf (2019), the belief that the world is a sphere contradict the Islamic principles, as such it should be rejected together with Darwinism and the philosophy that rain comes from water vanished the sun. To him, the group was initiated in 2002 in Maiduguri the state capital of Borno by Ustaz Mohammed Yusuf then. They later relocated to a village in Yobe state called Kanamma in 2004, where they established their base called "Afghanistan". It is from this base they used to organize and attack some nearby police outposts, killing police officers, burning churches and schools.

The activities of the Boko Haram insurgents have affected every sector in the Northern part of the country, Yobe state inclusive. It is also to be understood that even before the emergence of Boko Haram in Northeastern part of Nigeria, Nigeria was characterized with the highest rates of internal ethno religious and communal conflict in the world (Osaghae & Suberu, 2005). Right from the year 2009 to present time, the Boko Haram insurgency has confounded the North-East states of Nigeria, particularly Borno, Yobe and Adamawa (BAY) states, and other parts of the neighboring nations such as Lake Chad Region, Difa, Niger Republic, far Northern Cameroon and Chad, where millions of people were evacuated in the above-mentioned places, and turned tens of thousands of women and children to traumatized widows and orphans. This in addition according to Shehu (2018) that numerous houses, schools, educational facilities, villages were destroyed.

Problem Statement

The ongoing over a decade long Boko Haram insurgency is considered one of the most violent and destructive that has continued to pose serious threats to the Nigeria's internal and external security challenges. It is to be noted that numerous studies have investigated the effects and the impact of the insurgency in the Northeast region of Nigeria. (Mohammed, 2017; Ibrahim & Hamman-Obels, 2017; Usman & Dabai, 2020). In the same vein, Avis (2020) and Ibrahim and Hamman-Obels, (2017) have examined Boko Haram's various acts and forms of the destruction to education infrastructure, health facilities, markets and farms, closure of cattle markets, and restricted access to lands with consequent negative impact on livelihoods. In the view of these scholars the insurgency is considered to have adversely affected the developmental outcomes of the region. It is in this regard that Nwokolo (2022) emphasized that the security challenges have affected governance and economic growth in Nigeria having the Nigerian government spent at least ~~N~~8 trillion on security provisions in the most recent years to address security challenges in the country.

It is evident that since 2009, the persistent Boko Haram insurgency in North-Eastern Nigeria has led to the huge loss of lives and properties, destruction of critical infrastructure, displacement of millions, and the destabilization of most social, economic, health and education systems. Overall, these unfortunate developments have had negative effects and impacts on the productivity and development of the region and the nation at large. However, the consequences and impact of the attacks on the 6 states in the region has been different. For instance, the Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe (BAY) States have experienced much significant physical destruction and movements of displaced persons, which crippled their local

economies and livelihoods than Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba (BGT) states. In the BGT states of the region, they have been mostly affected by spill-over effect particularly from the point of movements of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) into their administrative boundary, which have imposed a large economic burden on the host states.

Prior to the year 2011, Yobe State was one of the most peaceful States in the country with its people in peaceful coexistence irrespective of ethnic, religious, or regional differences. However, towards the end of the year 2011, the State has become one of the theatres of raging insurgency against the Nigerian Nation-State. As a result of the unfortunate and senseless acts by the insurgents, Yobe State began to experience rampaging scorch-earth raids sometimes almost on daily basis. The Boko Haram raids have been experienced in 12 out of the 17 Local Government Areas of the State in various degrees. The affected Local Governments include Gubja, Gulani, Damaturu, Potiskum, Geidam, Yunusari, Fune, Fika, Nangere, Tarmuwa, Bade and Jakusko. In its peak in 2014, two of the local councils namely Gubja and Gulani were over ran by the Boko Haram insurgents, culminating in the routing of all security operatives and displacement of tens of thousands of the people in the area making them Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Damaturu, other Local Governments and neighbouring States of Gombe, Bauchi, Jigawa, Kano etc.

While various studies have been conducted to explore the effects and consequences of Boko Haram insurgency in the Northeast region of Nigeria, critical review of the past studies revealed a theoretical and empirical gap in their investigation on overall educational development. In most of the studies, they focused on causes of the insurgency, displacement, humanitarian condition of the IDPs among others (Mohammed, 2017; Ibrahim & Hamman-Obels, 2017; Usman & Dabai, 2020). Other scholars including Avis (2020) and Ibrahim and Hamman-Obels, (2017) have also examined Boko Haram's various acts and forms of the destruction to education infrastructure, health facilities, markets and farms, closure of cattle markets. To address this gap, this study therefore intends to explore the consequences of the Boko Haram insurgency in the region with emphasis on overall educational development especially as it affects death of teachers and students, destructions of school infrastructure and facilities, and displacements of teachers and students alike.

Research Methodology

Study Area

Yobe State is in the Northeast Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria. Situated within latitude and longitude 11°0 N and 13.50° E respectively, Yobe state was carved out of the old Borno State on 27th August 1991. The state covers an estimated area of 47,153 square kilometers that shares international boundaries to the North with the Republic of Niger, to the West with Jigawa and Bauchi States, to the East with Borno State, and to the south with Borno and Gombe States. As the second most affected state hit by the Boko Haram insurgency in the region, and with a considerable diverse population and having achieved relative peace and stability over the years, the Yobe state presents an interesting case for North-East region towards exploring the consequences of the Boko Haram insurgency in the region with emphasis on overall educational development.

With a projected 3.2% growth rate per annum, Yobe's population is about 4 million, having 70% of its population in the rural areas mostly engaged in agriculture respectively spread across its 17 Local Government Areas (NPC, 2008). Overall, farming, commerce, and trade are considered the main occupations of the citizens. Islam is the predominant religion of the citizens and Kanuri, Fulani, Hausa, Bade, Ngizim, Kare-Kare, Bolewa and Ngamo are their major ethnic groups. With 12% and 32% female and male literacy rate, Yobe like most Northern states in the Nigeria operates a pluralistic education system with both Islamic and western systems serving the populace.

For this paper, the methodology thus focuses on qualitative methods such as key informants' interviews of education and security stakeholders with basic expertise on education development especially as it

relates to the teachers and students' welfare, safety needs and concerns, technical requirements for infrastructure and facilities and displacement experts in the education cycle. This study therefore utilised the qualitative research approaches that offer in depth views of education and security stakeholders in their most real-life experience considered appropriate for this study.

Selection of Stakeholders

For this study, 48 education and security experts in the state and the region were involved through purposive sampling of different categories such as politicians: commissioners and legislators. Other categories involved policy makers and administrators: permanent secretaries, chief executives, and directors in the Ministry of Education (MoE) in addition to school principals and headmasters. Similarly, the civil society and education unions: National Union of Teachers (NUT); and School Based Management Committees (SBMC) were involved in addition to development partners: United Nations Children's Education Fund (UNICEF) and community, traditional and religious leaders. To address to security professional input, members of the security community both conventional and non-conventional were also involved.

Table 1. Categories of Education Stakeholders

Category	Number of stakeholders	Description of stakeholders
Politicians	6	Ruling & opposition party members
Senior administrators	6	MoE
Education providers	6	Professionals/support staff
Local civil society	6	Professionals & non-professional
Development partners	1	International/national/local
Community leaders	3	Traditional and religious
Total	28	Key Stakeholders

Table 2. Categories of Security Personnel

Category	Number of Securities	Description of Participants
Military Formations	4	Nigerian Army
Volunteers	4	Youth
State security services	3	State security services
Multinational joint taskforce (MJTF)	6	Military and Para Military
Vigilantes groups	3	Vigilantes' groups
Total	20	Security Agents

Data Collection

In-depth interviews of key education and security stakeholders and review of documents were utilized. The interviews mostly carried out in Northeast Nigeria lasted about 25-80 minutes at the stakeholder's places of convenience. Most questions posed were to understand the consequences of Boko Haram insurgency as it affects death, destruction, and displacement in the education sector. For the secondary sources of data, reviews on Yobe Socio-Economic Reform Agenda (YOSERA, 2008-2015); 2014 Education Sector Medium Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) and 2016 report on the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on education. Overall, the reviewed documents have provided this paper with relevant insights and guidance on the subject.

Data Analysis

The thematic analysis to qualitative research was utilised in this paper where the transcription and coding of themes were achieved on the stakeholder's interview transcripts and related documents. To achieve measurement credence, the 3Ds novelty was formulated to represent Death, Destruction and Displacement (DDD) while analysing each consequence on education development. This approach helped in identifying patterns and relationships between variables or themes that emerged from the

interview data and documents. Hence, systematic analysis of the data was majorly utilised to understand frameworks to analyse and discuss its major findings.

Data Analysis and Discussions

Deaths

All stakeholders interviewed showed deep concern about the issue of Boko Haram insurgency they experienced in Yobe State and North-east in general over the past years. The views were mostly informed by the fact that the unfortunate and dastardly act of the insurgents has caused huge loss of thousands lives, displacement of affected millions of people, destruction of properties belonging to Government and private individuals worth Trillions of Naira, loss of means of livelihood and psychological trauma. They all advanced that the combined effect of all these has culminated in serious socio-economic setbacks, threat to well-being and security of all citizens.

Taking into consideration the extent of destruction, these violent attacks by the Boko Haram insurgents have negative impact on educational sector in the North-East Zone particularly in Borno, Yobe and Adamawa states. The impact ranges from death of pupils, students, and staff across various affected educational institutions.

Table 3. Boko Haram’s Timeline of Attacks

Date	Place of Attack	Casualties	Nature of Attack
April 11, 2012	Yobe	-	Boko Haram attack and bombed Fika Primary school
August 19, 2012	Yobe	-	Boko Haram attacked and blew up the primary school in Damagum
September 6, 2012	Yobe	15 deaths	In a series of 6 coordinated attacks, the capital of Yobe state Boko Haram militant attack 2 primary schools killing approximately 15 students
October 18, 2012	Yobe	23 deaths	Boko Haram attacked an Islamic seminary school and 2 primary schools in Potiskum town killing approximately 23 students
October 25, 2012	Yobe	4 deaths	Boko Haram attacks Potiskum town and sporadically shooting into Chadi Primary school and killed 4 students
November 16, 2012	Yobe	-	Gasamu Science Boarding Primary School was attacked by Boko Haram, and they burnt 15 classrooms
June 18, 2013	Yobe	11 deaths	Boko Haram attacks GSS Damaturu, shooting sporadically, killing 7 students, 2 teachers and 2 gunmen. Headed to the staff quarters killing 2 another teacher, 6 students sustained various degrees of injuries
July 6, 2013	Yobe	42 deaths	Boko Haram attack GSS Mamudo in Potiskum LGA. killing 41 students and a teacher
July 6, 2013	Yobe	-	Boko haram set fire to the GSS Potiskum. Killing 46 school children’s and staffs and wounded 4 others
September 29, 2014	Yobe	41 deaths	Boko Haram stormed a dormitory of college of agriculture in Gujba. Killing 40 students and a teacher
February 25, 2014	Yobe	29 deaths	Boko Haram invaded a co-educational, FGC boarding school in Buni Yadi killing 29 male students, injured 59, abducted some female students, some girls ordered to quit school and get married or be killed in next attack
April 14 2014	Borno	Over 200 missing	GGSS Chibok was attacked, and more than 276 schoolgirls were kidnapped.
November 10, 2014	Yobe	49 deaths	Boko Haram attacks Potiskum town killing 49 student and injuring 75 in GSS Potiskum
February 19, 2018	Yobe	5 deaths	GGSS Dapchi was attacked, and more than 110 students were kidnapped.

March 21, 2018	Yobe	5 deaths	It was reported that out of 110 kidnaped students in GGSS Dapchi 105 were safely released and returned home by the kidnapers, and 5 were reported dead because of charge during the kidnapping
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Source: Researchers' Survey (2022) & Ali, Umaru, & Adamu, 2018; Dailytrust, 2018; Joseph Olukayode & Akinbi, 2015; Oladunjoye & Omemu, 2013 & Ajayi, 2011).

The above Table indicates the timeline of Boko Haram attacks on educational institutions across Yobe State and the Chibok girl's abduction that resulted in deaths of pupils, students, teachers, and destruction school infrastructure. While the exact number of persons killed by the Boko Haram terrorists through bomb attacks, suicide explosions, gun shots, arson or those caught in crossfire has not been ascertained with any accuracy to date, available records of students killed from Government Secondary School Mamudo, Federal Government College, Buni-Yadi, College of Agriculture, Gujba, Government Science Senior Secondary School, Potiskum and Government Science Secondary School Damaturu is 128. It is therefore considerate to say that past year's reign of terror unleashed by Boko Haram has caused uncountable loss of lives and limbs running into thousands.

The findings of this study are consistent with many previous findings in other contexts where conflict affects educational development. In Iraq for instance, Diwakar (2015) studied the effect of armed conflict on education from experience of Iraq that shows the devastating effects of conflict on human capital formation and the development of education. The findings of the study revealed that the conflict has led to the destruction of various school infrastructure, displacement and deaths of pupils, students, and education administrators. Although various efforts were made by the government even at the time of the crisis to recruit more teachers, the security challenges have compounded an already existing wide gap in the teacher/pupil/student's ratio. As a demonstration of commitment to address the education manpower shortage in the state, the government has over the years embarked on the massive recruitment of university graduates, Higher National Diploma (HND) and Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) holders to provide quality manpower for the education sector in Yobe state. This teacher's union leaders explained.

In 2013 alone, Governor Gaidam had given approval for the massive employment of more than 2000 NCE holders. In the process of screening the applicant teachers, we were able to realise about 1600 as qualified teachers. They (teacher applicants) were immediately recruited and posted out indiscriminately across the 17 LGAs in Yobe state most especially across primary and junior secondary schools' levels. This is the first time in the history of Yobe such massive teacher recruitment was undertaken by any political regime democratic or military. This, we hope will add value to our current education development.

Having regards to the efforts in employment of teachers the big question was whether the current number of teachers are adequate especially with regards to teacher/student ratio (UNESCO 1:40 ratio)? Importantly, under a democratic arrangement, the central government of most nations through their national policies on education develops such teacher/student ratio based on international standards (Carson et al, 2015). As a way of education provision decentralization at sub-national levels, the state governments are responsible for operationalising these educational standards (Carson et al, 2015) based on the UNESCO and their national education development goals.

Most stakeholders were of the view that, the Boko Haram insurgency have added to the existing shortage of teachers which is considered as an important human resource for education remains a lingering national challenge in the education sector over the years in Nigeria. In a 2014 education MTSS report, it was projected that between 2011 and 2015 alone, Nigeria needed 212,000 primary school teachers with required qualifications (YBSG, 2014a). This report further revealed that at the pace at which the current education sector was heading, Nigeria may not fill the gap even by 2030. The above points are indication that there is shortage of teachers in the Nigerian education sector as well as in Yobe state which is considered a national problem that needs serious attention.

With the death of many males headed households because of the Boko Haram insurgency, many women are now widows and children orphans. The widows and orphans are people that lost their lives because of the Boko Haram activities. Shehu (2018) disclosed that Boko Haram insurgency has led to a huge number of orphaned children and widows. It is observed that 60% of all the peoples in the IDPs established because of Boko Haram insurgency are women and children. Similarly, 60% of all the children in those camps are orphans and such children are encountering a lot of problems which include but not limited to socio-psychological, medical, economic, and ecological trials because of this. Zastrow and Ashman (2010) observed that abandoned children suffer from or are victims of physical and mental health care, and educationally deserted, without appropriate and regular life management, they as well face housing dangers, and they lack good household and basic individual and hygiene, face social and attachment difficulties, at the same time they lack basic nourishment, meet mental and academic shortfalls, and have expressive and social problems.

Another problem of the insurgent's group epoch is the presence of ignored or unaccompanied children all over the affected state's towns and communities inclusive and extended to some neighboring areas. Nevertheless, it is understood that many orphans were displaced all over the northeastern region, many of them are abused in one form or the other and in extensive poverty and children and women are poorest in pretentious places. In a report from the (NEMA, 2015), it revealed that there are over 5,000 orphans in the North-Eastern region of Nigeria alone. These children/orphans if not immediately catered for may likely grow up unschooled, impoverished for life challenges, jobless, and crooks as well as counterproductive to the Nigerian state and society (Badiora, 2017).

Destruction

Over the years, the unfortunate and dastardly act by the Boko Harm insurgents has according to all the informants resulted in the destruction of public and private properties/assets worth Trillions of Naira spread across Northeastern region. In Yobe state, while most social and economic sectors of the society were affected, the total number of public buildings and facilities destroyed across the affected 11 Local Governments Areas in the State stands at 1,098 with education sector having the highest destruction of 609 school infrastructure and facilities followed by the health sector (Abbas, 2017). The study revealed 55.5% of the public and private infrastructures destroyed by insurgents in the state were in the education sector (YBSG, 2016) that should be rebuilt. The following tables indicate selected tertiary institutions, secondary schools and primary schools that have been attacked by the Boko Haram insurgents across the state.

Table 4. Some Affected Tertiary Institutions

S/N	Name of institution	LGA
1	Mai Idriss Aloomo Polytechnic Geidam	Geidam LGA
2	College of Agriculture Gujba	Gujba LGA
3	College of Administrative & Business Studies, Potiskum	Potiskum LGA
4	Yobe State University Damaturu	Damaturu LGA

Table 5. Some Affected Secondary Schools

S/N	Name of school	Location	LGA
1	Federal Government College	Buni-Yadi	Gujba
2	Government Junior Secondary School	Buni-Yadi	Gujba
3	Government Secondary School	Goniri	Gujba
4	Best Centre Geidam	Geidam	Geidam
5	Government Junior Secondary School	Kanamma	Yunusari
6	Government Science & Technical School	Gujba	Gujba
7	Best Centre Goniri	Goniri	Gujba
8	Government Day Secondary School	Kukuwa	Gulani
9	Government Junior Secondary School	Bularafa	Gulani

10	Government Science Secondary School	Bularafa	Gulani
11	Best Centre Potiskum	Potiskum	Potiskum
12	FCE(I) Demonstration School	Potiskum	Potiskum
13	Best Centre Potiskum	Potiskum	Potiskum
14	Government Secondary School	Mamudo	Potiskum
15	Government Science Secondary School	Damaturu	Damaturu

Table 6. Some Affected Primary Schools (Gujba LGA)

S/N	Primary Schools in Gujba LGA	Primary Schools Gujba LGA
1	Kasatchiya Primary School	Mutai Primary School
2	Central Primary School Buni Yadi	Wagir Primary School
3	Shuwari Primary School	Katorko Primary School
4	Gujba Primary School	Azare Primary School
5	Malam Bello Primary School Goniri	Marma Primary School
6	Gotala Primary School	Ambiya Kura Primary School
7	Ambiya Tasha Primary Sch.	Kukawa Primary School
8	Maina Ngubtori Primary School	Goni Maruri Primary School
9	Kadauri Primary School	M. Dunari Primary School
10	Ngurbuwa Primary School	Goni Ngomari Primary School.

Table 7. Some Affected Primary Schools (Damaturu LGA & Potiskum LGA)

S/N	Primary Schools in Damaturu LGA	Primary Schools in Potiskum LGA
1	Modu Mustapha	Ari-kime Primary School
2	Bindigari	Chadi Primary School
3	Central Primary School	Mai Adiko Primary School
4	Pompomari Primary Sch.	Nahuta Primary School
5	Abba Primary School	Racecourse Primary School
6	Nayi-Nawa Primary Sch.	Sabon Layi Primary School
7	Bukar Ali Primary School	Yindiski Primary School
8	Ali Marami	
9	Kukareta	
10	Bulabulin Primary School	

Table 8. Some Affected Primary Schools (Gulani LGA & Fune LGA)

S/N	Primary Schools in Gulani LGA	Primary Schools in Fune LGA
1	Bularafa Primary School	Daura Primary School
2	Boarding Primary School Bara	Garin Baushe Primary School
3	Gabai Primary School	Damagum Central Primary School
4	Dokshi Primary School	Dogon Kuka "A" Primary School

Table 9. Some Affected Primary Schools (Gulani LGA & Fune LGA)

S/N	Primary Schools in Fika LGA	Primary Schools in Yunusari LGA
1	Fika Primary School, Fika	Kanamma Primary School I
2	Fika II Primary School	Kanamma Primary School II

In Yobe state, some of the schools attacked include Bindigari Primary School, Central Primary School, Damaturu, Government Day Secondary School, Damaturu, and Government Secondary School Mamudo. Federal Government College Buni Yadi and College of Agriculture, Gujba were also attacked that also led to their relocation to another school in another local government area. Usman, Ibrahim, and Yerima (2018) examined the effects of insurgency on basic education facilities in Mandaragirau District, Biu, Local Government Area of Borno State that indicated that the emergence of Boko haram attacks on schools with bombs in Mandaragirau District, Biu LGA had resulted into killing, abducting, and kidnapping of school children in the area creating fear and displacement of families in the locality. The

study further revealed that schools in the area were indefinitely closed during the peak period of insurgency, and this has significantly affected the day to day running of the schools and consequently affecting education of children in the area.

In a study by Usman and Dabai in 2020, *Boko Haram Insurgency: Repercussions on Educational Institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria* interrogated the repercussion of Boko Haram attacks on educational institutions in Adamawa State. The study discovered that the attacks have affected academic activities, structures, manpower and coping strategies of the affected institutions. The attack on schools have led to the destruction of classrooms building, schools records, instruction materials and loss of lives of the teachers, pupils, students, and displacement, and thereby affecting educational achievements at various levels (Mohammed, 2017). Similarly, according to former Governor of Borno State Kashim Shettima, at least 800 classrooms have been burnt and 179 teachers killed (as cited in Mohammed, 2017:56). All these attacks on the educational facilities and infrastructure have continued to negatively affect conducive teaching and learning atmosphere.

Displacement

Most informants agreed albeit without government accurate record or data that the attacks of the Boko Haram Insurgents have resulted in the displacement of over Three Hundred Thousand (300,000) people and psychological trauma, making them Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Yobe State. Most government approximate record show that the most of the IDPs are mainly of Gujba, Gulani, Geidam, Yunusari and Damaturu Local Government origin, and have some point in time either resided in other Local Governments in the State, Maiduguri in Borno State, and neighbouring States of Gombe, Bauchi, Jigawa, etc. However, with improved security situation in the State, many IDPs that were hitherto residing elsewhere have returned to their original settlements.

While even at the peak of the Boko Haram insurgency in Yobe state, the State government had always discouraged IDP Camp settlement notably in two official camps of Pompomari and Bukar Ibn Ali Primary Schools, Damaturu. Furthermore, about 22,097 Internally Displaced Persons were residing at self-set camps situated in Alhaji Muhammadu Gombe's farm, Fuguri, Ngaburwa, Kukareta and adjacent to Abbari/Yobe Broadcasting Corporation complex. Infact, an over 280,000 Internally Displaced Persons lived in host communities a lot of whom are from Borno State, while there were considerable number of IDPs residing in Borno, Gombe, Bauchi Jigawa Kano and beyond.

The impact of the attacks on the six states in the region has been different. Borno, Adamawa and Yobe (BAY) States have experienced significant physical destruction and forced movements of displaced persons, which crippled their local economies and livelihoods. Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba (BGT) states have been affected by the spill-over effect of the conflict particularly from the displacement of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) into their administrative boundary, which have imposed a large social and economic burden on the host states, World Bank, 2015; (as cited in Avis, 2020).

Overall, the insurgent activities have displaced about 3 million people and responsible for approximately 350,000 deaths in Northeast Nigeria. According to a National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) report, insurgents have destroyed over 254 schools in Northeast Nigeria. The conflict was also responsible for drop out of 120,000 students from attending schools (Nwokolo, 2022). Though, the deaths attributed to Boko Haram violence have substantially decreased since the sect's activity peaked in 2014. The group has been pushed out from several Northeast states and local governments by the Nigerian army in collaboration with neighboring countries like Benin, Cameroon, Chad, and Niger. According to the 2022 Global Terrorism Index (GTI), Nigeria improved from the fourth position in 2021 to sixth in 2022 (Nwokolo, 2022).

One of the most pronounced activities of the Boko Haram insurgents is the attack on schools and abduction of girls and boys in Schools across the region. Lauren Ploch Blanchard (2014) disclosed that in 2013 the attacks became more ruthless, gradually aiming students and teachers in schools in the northern region. He revealed that in July 2013, Boko Haram's leader openly endangered to burn nonspiritual institutions and kill their teachers, describing the schools as a "plot against Islam." This

menace has discouraged thousands of children from attending school in the region that already had low turnout rates and literacy levels, especially among women and girls. National statistics unveiled vast differences within Nigeria in the percentage of girls who attend school, with attendance lowest in the northern region. yet, in the same year 2013, the insurgent's attacked Government Girl's Secondary School in Chibok and kidnapped over 260 students. Though, it was not the first time Boko Haram abducted women in Nigeria, however, those kidnapped were later forced to convert to Islam by the group and have been used as sex objects by a terrorist group.

A few months after the Chibok abduction, specifically on February 25, 2014, 58 male students at the Federal Government College Buni Yadi were also abducted by the Boko Haram militants. On that fateful day, many young students were killed in their dormitory. In February 2018 over 110 girls were abducted from Government Secondary school in Dapchi of Yobe state. The group later negotiated with the federal government on the release of the abducted girls where 109 abducted Dapchi girls out of this 110 safely returned, 5 reported dead due to stampede during the abduction, and one girl still held hostage (Dailytrust, 2018 pp 4). Considering the number of the abducted girls and boys from the 3 secondary schools this has affected the lives of many young women and boys in the northern region by discouraging parents from sending their wards to schools.

Considering the negative activities of Boko Haram activities on northern Nigeria the study noted that most of the children that lost their parents are facing challenges, such as child abuse, and trauma due to broken home among others. These affected children as the future leaders if not properly counselled and guided may grow up in this situation that may affect the society at large. In addition, many young girls and women were raped by either the Boko Haram sect, security agents and or some agents of the international donors. In relation to child abuse, it is observed that most of the children are drop out from the school because their parents are killed by the Boko Haram insurgents, and no one to take care of them, or sponsor their education. Impliedly, if these set of people are without education and parental care, they may become a nuisance in the society.

The activities of the insurgent group are not limited to security agents, but the students in the various school have been attacked, however, attack on one school or nearby villages put a fear in the minds of students and the people living in the environment, that any school or villages in the area might be attacked. A study by Ugwumba and Odom (2015) disclosed that Boko Haram insurgents repeated attacks on several schools across the northeastern region of the nation and this has an insuperable obstacle to education for a large number of children. He added that the psychosocial impact will affect children's ability to study, and the places where these activities continue may lead to their (pupils/students) withdrawal from school, even if the school remains open, most of the children cannot be allowed to attain school because of the fear of future occurrence.

Mahmood, (2021) examined the impact of Boko Haram Insurgency on Educational Activities in Borno State. The findings showed that, just like in Yobe state, Boko Haram insurgency have negatively affected student's enrollment in most public secondary schools in Maiduguri Borno State thereby contributing to low school attendance and responsible for destruction of school facilities and infrastructure. The study therefore suggests restoring normalcy and giving parents the confidence to send their wards to school; government and security agents should be vigilant on what is happening in the society and security agents should provide special attention to the schools and students of the region. All the necessary actions are to be geared towards protecting the school students and pupils from physical harm and psychological attacks of the Boko Haram insurgency.

It is important to note that several attacks that took place in Northeastern part of the nation reveals the vulnerability and exposed nature of the Nigeria's school children and its population. Since the widely media circulated attacks on the school children by the abduction of the Chibok girls and others that follow, many are of the view that it has become a defining moment for the country as mass abduction is no longer an isolated case either by extreme ideology, political vendetta or criminality have become a daily reoccurrence in Nigeria. With an increased armed banditry in Northwest and North Central, communities and families have been shattered as they all live in fear and anxiety. It is most worrisome to

note that since then, there have been series of mass abductions of school children spread in various communities across Northern Nigeria as capture below:

Table 10. Timeline of Mass Abduction of School Children in Nigeria

Date	Place of Abduction	Casualties	Nature of Abduction
December 11, 2020	Katsina	300	Gun men on motorbikes stormed Government Science Secondary (boys boarding) in Kankara and abducted 300 students. The students were later released.
February 17, 2021	Niger	41	Armed bandits targeted Government Science College in Kagara and abducted 41 persons including students, staff members and their family. They were later released after alleged negotiations.
February 26, 2021	Zamfara	300	Over 300 schoolgirls were abducted at the Government Girls Secondary School Jangebe in Zamfara state. Few days later the government announced their release.
May 30, 2021	Niger	150	Armed bandits attacked an Islamic school Salihu Tanko Islamic School in Rafi LGA of Niger State and abducted over 150 students. While some have died in captivity, other students were said to be released after alleged negotiation.
July 17, 2021	Kebbi	Dozens	Some gun men attacked Federal Government College Birnin Yawuri and abducted dozens of unknown numbers of students and teachers. In the incidents a police officer was killed and injured several others in the process of the abduction. The Army rescued some, other released after alleged payment of ransom.
July 5, 2021	Kaduna	-	Some students and staff of Bethel Baptist High School Damishi in Kaduna state were abducted in the late evening hours.
January 20, 2023	Nasarawa	6	Some gunmen were said to have attacked a Local Government Education Authority primary where 6 students were abducted. Few days later the abducted students were rescued.
January 30, 2024	Ekiti		Some gunmen attacked the school bus of Apostolic Faith Secondary School in Ekiti where unknown number of pupils, teacher and the bus driver were abducted. Four days later, the pupils and their teacher were rescued but the driver was dead.
March 7, 2024	Kaduna	287	Gunmen attacked Government Secondary School Kuriga, Chikun LGA in Kaduna state and abducted 287 students while one vigilante was killed in the process. Some weeks later, the students were released as announced by the State Government.
March 9, 2024	Sokoto	15	Some gunmen attacked a Tsangaya school in Gidan Bakuso in Gada LGA in Sokoto state and abducted 15 students. After 14 days in captivity, they were reportedly rescued during a military operation.

Source: The Cable, Timeline: 11 high profile abductions of school children after Chibok tragedy, April 14, 2024.

Major Findings, Implications and Conclusions

It is evident that since 2009, the persistent Boko Haram insurgency in North-Eastern Nigeria has led to the huge loss of lives and properties, destruction of critical infrastructure, displacement of millions, and the destabilization of most social, economic, health and education systems. Overall, these unfortunate developments have had negative effects and impacts on the productivity and development of the region and the nation at large. However, the consequences and impact of the attacks on the 6 states in the region have been different. For instance, the Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe (BAY) States have experienced much significant physical destruction and movements of displaced persons, which crippled their local

economies and livelihoods than Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba (BGT) states. In the BGT states of the region, they have been mostly affected by spill-over effect particularly from the point of movements of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) into their administrative boundary, which have imposed a large economic burden on the host states.

The study found that there are several associated consequences of Boko Haram insurgency on education in the region including but not limited to death, destruction, and displacement of pupils, students, teachers, and many other education stakeholders alike. The consequences have had serious implications on education manpower shortage, destruction of school infrastructure and facilities, and displacement or abduction of teachers and students, among others. It is noted that these consequences have repeatedly posed a serious threat or set back to conducive teaching and learning environment much needed for by teachers and students alike and by extension to the education sector at large. The attacks and destruction of the affected schools have serious final implications as the cost of rebuilding these destroyed school infrastructure by the Boko Haram insurgents and the support provide to security agencies for the war against terror remains one of the most herculean challenges.

Although the effects of insecurity are negative on general social welfare services due to diversion of meager resource for security matters, it should be noted that this is not an exclusive case or phenomenon to Yobe state. Like in the case of most conflict affected areas WDI (2014) revealed that as wars in the globe are witnessed, major public spending on education was cut due to increase in budget for defence (Diwakar, 2015). In fact, this scenario was similarly reported in Iraq (Diwakar, 2015). In Yobe state alone, it means without the Boko Haram insurgency, over N12 Billion spent by 2015 on providing support for the security agencies, would have been used to provide other social welfare services such as education and health being regarded an important social welfare development positive for achieving democratic consolidation in most developing societies.

Another aspect of the consequences of the Boko Haram insurgency on education development is on educational achievements in the national qualifying examinations results in Senior Secondary School Examination (SSCE) in for example West African Examination Council (WAEC), National Examination Council (NECO) and Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB). Its relevance is that to be eligible for higher education the students must pass WAEC or in some cases NECO with 5 credits including English and Mathematics. This means access to higher education for students in Yobe state, Northeast and Nigeria is determined by the pass credit acquire in national examinations. Using WAEC result analysis from 2011 to 2015 in the state, its annual data show the proportion of students passing the examinations is very low. While this ugly scenario is not only peculiar to Yobe state as most northern states in the country have always recorded lower educational achievements compared to their southern counterparts (MDG, 2015; UNDP, 2015, UNICEF, 2015), the case of Yobe State and the Northeast region has been worst over the years.

Similarly, the attacks by Boko Haram insurgents have affected most schools' academic activities, structures, manpower and coping strategies of the affected institutions. The consistent attacks on schools have led to the destruction of classrooms building, schools records, instruction materials and loss of lives of the teachers, pupils, students, and their displacement, and thereby affecting educational achievements at various levels (Mohammed, 2017). In most cases, when schools are attacked, they must be relocated to a safer space in another location to continue with their regular academic activities. These attacks on the educational facilities and infrastructure have continued to negatively affect conducive teaching and learning atmosphere in most of the conflict affected areas.

Another implication of the insurgent's attacks on schools and communities is the presence of many ignored or unaccompanied children scattered all over the region's towns and communities and extended to some neighboring areas. It is understood that many orphans who are of school age bracket are displaced in northeastern region, many of them abused in one form or the other and in an extensive poverty situation. In a report by NEMA (2015), it revealed that there are over 5,000 orphans in the North-Eastern region alone. These children/orphans if not immediately and properly catered for may likely

grow up unschooled, impoverished for life challenges, jobless, and crooks, and may also serve as counterproductive to the Nigerian state and society (Badiora, 2017).

The findings of this study are consistent with many previous findings in other contexts where conflict affects education and educational development in general. Diwakar (2015) studied the effect of armed conflict on education from experience of Iraq that shows the devastating effects of conflict on human capital formation and the development of education. The findings revealed that the conflict has led to the destruction of various school infrastructure, displacement and deaths of pupils, students, and education administrators. Although various efforts were made by the state and federal government even at the time of the crisis to recruit more teachers, provide infrastructure, enroll more pupil and students, improve school access and student's performance, the security challenges caused by the Boko Haram insurgency have further compounded an already existing wide gap in the education development mix of the region in the comity of others in Nigeria.

To advance a conducive teaching and learning atmosphere in the states across the Northeast region, it is recommended that government and stakeholders must work hand in hand to provide practical and realistic steps that will address the recurring Boko Harm and other related security challenges associated with schools and education development in general. It is believed that with an enhanced safe and conducive learning space for teachers and students alike their performance in major education outcomes will improve as well enhance the overall educational development not only in the Northeast region but across Nigeria as a whole. The task of enhanced security towards uplifting educational development in the region remains a task that must be achieved through mutual partnerships, collaboration and commitment by all stakeholders and concerned in the Nation.

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